

POLLUTION OF SURFACE WATERS OF UKRAINE

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Abstract

Protection of the water environment is a priority task today. The issue of water pollution is relevant for Ukraine. Whole ecosystems suffer due to the pollution of surface water, and the consumption of poisoned water is dangerous for human life. This work is devoted to the topic of water pollution of Ukraine. The main causes of pollution are considered. Steps to overcome environmental problems are proposed.

Keywords: wastewater, sources of water pollution

Drinking water is one of the most valuable resources today. Since Ukraine belongs to the countries with an insufficient level of water resources provision, the issue is gaining relevance. their preservation. As a result of intense anthropogenic load, there is constant pollution of surface and underground waters.

Table 1, formed on the basis of data from the state water use accounting, shows the volumes of return water discharges to Ukraine in the period 2018-2021. Despite the fact that there is a clear tendency to decrease the total volume of discharged return water and the polluted categories in particular, the volumes of wastewater remain quite significant.

Table 1

Volumes of return (wastewater) discharges in Ukraine

Volumes of discharged return water, million m ³	2018	2019	2020	2021
That's all	5210	5374	5159	4684,6
Contaminated	952	737	518	541,5

The main sources of water pollution are agriculture, industry and household waste. Agricultural effluents from farms and agricultural productions contain a large percentage of organic matter. Livestock waste belongs to hazardous waste due to its high infectiousness. If the waste water from the production enters the treatment facilities, where it will be completely or partially cleaned, then it is impossible to control the washing off from the agricultural land and seepage into the ground of the waste stored in the open air. With rainwater, pesticide residues, mineral fertilizer components and manure components enter underground and later surface water through the soil. In surface water bodies, these substances cause the process of eutrophication, poison the water and make it unsafe for consumption. Wastewater from enterprises, factories, and plants differs significantly in composition and properties, depending on the type of industry, raw materials, and technological process. Water pollution by heavy metals and petroleum products is a particular problem for Ukrainian rivers. A serious problem related to domestic wastewater is the outdated equipment of treatment facilities.

This phenomenon leads to the fact that untreated or partially treated wastewater enters rivers, causing biological pollution of water bodies. Rivers in Southern and Eastern Ukraine are characterized by a higher level of pollution, which is associated with a large number of agricultural lands and industrial facilities. So, the pollution of water resources of Ukraine is a serious problem today. The use of often outdated and malfunctioning cleaning equipment leads to the gradual poisoning of water bodies. Reconstruction and modernization of treatment facilities is necessary. It is also necessary to conduct constant monitoring of the state of small rivers, which ultimately significantly affect the state of the main rivers of the country.

References

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